

**AUTONOMIC TRACKING:
METHODOLOGICAL VIABILITY
OF AN ALTERNATIVE
EPISTEMOLOGICAL APPROACH**

A WHITE PAPER

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ABSTRACT

The ancestral/ Indigenous art and science of hard-ground tracking provides an epistemic mode directly applicable to the moment-to-moment tracking of human autonomic nervous system structure and function. This mode can be applied as a primary, empirically verifiable way of knowing to apprehend more about the structure and function of the living nervous system. Its systemic application has informed the development of Autonomics.

ARGUMENT

It is considered axiomatic in the field of neurology, as presently prosecuted in modernity, that validated medical knowledge about the structure and function of the nervous system comes to us from cadaver dissection. And in the recent (2007-2026) Polyvagal debate^[1], Stephen W. Porges, PhD, and Paul Grossman argue about neuro-anatomical structure and function based on differing inferences from comparative evolutionary neuro-anatomy. Both sets of arguments rely heavily on inference drawn from two hundred million years of vertebrate evolution, and conjectures about the migration of clusters of neurons in the brainstem over spans of evolutionary time. Both of these methods (cadaver dissection and comparative neuro-anatomy), considered de rigueur, have the unfortunate baseline requirement of investigating nervous systems that are dead.

Fortunately for all of us, there is a much more direct, experiential, and phenomenological methodology available for the exploration of the structure and function of dedicated neural circuits, one that takes advantage of unique and time-tested epistemological methods for accruing knowledge about an environment, and permits validation through empirical confirmation.

For 99% of the lineage history of humans, during which we existed in small band hunter gatherer tribes (SBHG), humans have engaged for survival in nature awareness practices that included hard-ground tracking. Hard-ground tracking, or simply 'tracking' is considered by many Indigenous communities as a

1 Grossman et al., 2026. <https://www.clinicalneuropsychiatry.org/download/why-the-polyvagal-theory-is-untenable-an-international-expert-evaluation-of-the-polyvagal-theory-and-commentary-upon-porges-s-w-2025-polyvagal-theory-current-status-clinical-applications-and/>

Porges, 2026. <https://www.clinicalneuropsychiatry.org/download/when-a-critique-becomes-untenable-a-scholarly-response-to-grossman-et-al-s-evaluation-of-polyvagal-theory/>

the animal is moving across the landscape. This mode, which synthesizes information from the extero-senses (sight, sounds, smell, taste, touch) with inner modes of sensory awareness (interoception, proprioception, vestibular sense, inward listening) merges with deep ecological knowledge of place and pattern recognition to ignite a meta-capacity: this is the FEEL of a great tracker. A sensitized and verifiable accurate moment-to-moment ability to FEEL what the animal is doing. Whether or not the FEEL of a tracker is accurately calibrated is easy to determine by whether or not the tracker locates the animal at the end of the trail.

This empirical verifiability of a tracker's skillset is requisite to the enterprise, because anyone can say that they know where the animal is: the tracker is the one who actually finds it.

AUTONOMIC TRACKING

The translation research firm that I direct, Hearth Science, applies tracking as an epistemic mode to the embodied nervous system, particularly its moment-to-moment autonomic transformations. Because the autonomic nervous system MUST express its moment-to-moment state dynamically through each inhalation and exhalation, and because its dynamic alteration in response to internal and external stimuli change

- breathing rate and depth
- oxygenation
- capillary dilation
- modulation of venous and arterial flows
- piloerection/shivering
- heartrate and heartbeat intensity
- muscle tension
- gesture
- posture
- vocal prosody
- eye gaze

- pupillary dilation
- galvanic skin response
- movement of the head and neck
- axial tilt of the head on the neck
- tuning of the middle ear
- the surfacing of protective, reflex, spontaneous, archetypal, and hardwired spinal motor gestures
- availability of interoceptive sensation throughout the body entire (interoceptive competence)
- absence of interoceptive sensation throughout the body entire (interoceptive deficit)
- proprioceptive competence
- proprioceptive deficit
- vestibular sense or its absence
- visceral regulation of organ systems
- tension of the various diaphragms of the body
- retention or dissipation of allostatic loads
- digestive motility
- emotional range
- modes of cognition
- perception of the world around us
- behavioral repertoire expressed
- meaning-making and interpretation of our experience
- expressed neurochemistry ambient in the blood
- apnea during shutdown responses
- and more...

It is possible to apply the epistemic mode of hard ground tracking to moment-to-moment monitoring and modulation of the Autonomic Nervous System. A trained autonomic tracker, working with a client of reasonable sensitivity and sufficient physiological & mental health, can engage in a dyadic process of tracking the autonomic nervous system of the client to support its movement in the direction of health, growth, and restoration in realtime through non-invasively

- potentiating salutogenic autonomic states
- facilitating the completion of self-protective and other incomplete motor gestures linked to retained 'fight-or-flight' allostatic loads, including hardwired spinal autonomic reset

repertoires

- facilitating the return to baseline from the repertoire of global and localized shutdown responses (shutdown, placating, tonic immobility)

A trained group of autonomic trackers, working with a clinical population of sufficient size, can begin to make categorical observations about the pattern language of the structure and function of the human nervous system through repeated observation of its expressed autonomic pattern language.

Since, neurologically speaking, there is tight functional fit between present moment autonomic state and expressed autonomic repertoire (an autonomic state is the preferential tuning of the bodymind to highly conserve energy in response to specific contextual conditions), the epistemic mode of tracking can reveal to us the functional neurophysiological coordination of various autonomic states.

It can be directly observed that coordination in this regard evidences neurological linkage. Ergo a novel empirically verifiable non-invasive methodology for reverse-engineering the underlying neural pathways.

By observing the transitions between autonomic state, e.g., from flight response back to social engagement (connection state), or from shutdown response through fight response back to social engagement, or from shutdown response through union back to social engagement, we can discern the proximity/relatedness of various neural circuits and observe their response sequencing. **This method provides an alternate non-invasive and empirically verifiable methodology for testing hypotheses about autonomic state composition, organization, and response hierarchies.**

In our new foundation model of autonomic physiology (June 2024) Hearth Science has deployed this epistemic mode of autonomic tracking to assemble a novel *in vivo* cartography of

the functional neuro-anatomy of the living autonomic nervous system, its expressed neurochemistry, and the pattern language of the composition of autonomic state as an integral of autonomic temperature (moment-to-moment neurological determination of safety, danger, and lifethreat), recruited neurological systems, and recruited neurochemistry.

This autonomic model is, like the work of a hardground tracker, experientially verifiable without required recourse to theoretical models or inference. It can be observed directly, in realtime, in living persons. With Autonomics we can work directly and non-invasively on the expressed moment-to-moment pattern language of the ANS. Its extraordinary efficacy in treating stress-related disorders is the primary evidence of its accuracy.

CONCLUSION

While the validation models of traditional autonomic neuroscience rely on a) necrotic anatomy, or b) evolutionary inference, there exists a non-invasive, direct, embodied, empirically verifiable method of testing anatomical and functional linkages in the living autonomic nervous system. Utilizing an epistemological mode with its roots in traditional hard-ground tracking, the art and science of autonomic tracking can bring us new and verifiable knowledge about the living structure and function of the autonomic nervous system.

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